

Point Defect Interaction in Dilute beta-Zirconium Alloys

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Solute vacancy interaction changes the vacancy concentration and also alters the jump frequencies of the solvent atoms in its vicinity. The nature and the extent of interaction can be inferred from the changes in the solvent diffusivity as a function of solute content.

In this paper, the effect of different solutes (V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Nb and Sn) on the solvent diffusivity in beta phase of zirconium has been discussed.

IN an alloy, the field in the vicinity of a solute atom is different from that of the solvent atom. The probability of a vacancy existing near the solute atom will be more or less compared to the solvent atom depending on whether there is solute-vacancy attraction or repulsion. In addition to this, the solvent-vacancy exchange frequency in the neighbourhood of the solute will be different than away from it.

The perturbed solvent jump frequencies together with the changes in the vacancy concentration will determine the change in the solvent diffusivity. Method of calculations of certain jump frequency ratios and correlation factor for the solute (f_1) for the dilute alloys of zirconium in (beta) body centred cubic phase have been given in the following section. The former throws light on solute-vacancy interaction and the latter on the mechanism of diffusion. It was found that for certain systems, the vacancy mechanism is not valid and for them the minimum value of b for vacancy mechanism to be valid, has been reported. The solute-vacancy binding energies for different solutes where vacancy mechanism of diffusion is operative, are also given.

Calculations :

For body centred cubic metals, it is desirable to consider solute vacancy interaction upto second neighbours as the difference of distances between the first and the second neighbour is small. Eight types of solvent jump frequencies and fourteen types of solvent jumps in the vicinity of the solute atoms are normally considered (Fig. 1). W_3, W'_3 and W''_3 are the jump frequencies for the dissociative jumps to the second, third and fifth neighbour positions while W_4, W'_4 and W''_4 are the jump frequencies for associative jump opposite to W_3, W'_3 and W''_3 , respectively. The jump frequency W_8 is for the dissociative jumps from the second neighbour sites to the fourth neighbour sites, whereas W_6 is for jumps opposite to W_8 . The fourteen types of jumps differ either in jump frequency or differ in X component or both. The fourteen partial correlation factors (f_1, f_2, \dots, f_{14}) will be functions of five jump frequency ratios, e.g. $W_3/W_2, W_3/W'_3, W'_3/W''_3, W_4/W_5$ and W'_4/W_0 . b will be function of these jump

Fig. 1. Different solvent jump frequencies (W_s, W'_s, \dots) and different types of solvent jumps (1, 2, \dots) in presence of solute (●). The Roman numerals indicate, 1st, 2nd, etc. neighbours, while arrows show the vacancy jump direction.

frequency ratios and will also depend on partial correlation factors¹.

Under certain simplifying assumptions, b and partial correlation factors can be written as functions of two jump frequency ratios instead of five. These assumptions have been discussed by Le Claire² and he has suggested two models.

In model 1, solute-vacancy interaction upto second nearest neighbour separation is considered and all the jumps to the first and second neighbour from more distant sites are supposed to occur with pure solvent jump frequency W_0 , i.e. $W'_4 = W''_4 = W_6 = W_0$ and $W'_3 = W''_3$. In model 2, interactions upto the first nearest neighbour separation only are considered and all the dissociative jumps from the first nearest neighbour site of the solute occur with the same frequency, i.e. $W_5 = W_6 = W_0, W_3 = W'_3 = W''_3$ and $W_4 = W'_4 = W''_4$.

In model 1, b , $D_1/D(o)$ and f_1 can be written as a function³ of W_2/W'_2 and W_3/W'_3 ,

$$b = -20 + 14(\mu_1/f_0) + 6(\nu_1/f_0)(W_3/W'_3) \quad (1)$$

$$D_1/D(o) = (W_2/W'_2)(u/f_0)/(u + 2W_2/W'_2) \quad (2)$$

$$\text{and } f_1 = u/(u + 2W_2/W'_2) \quad (3)$$

where,

$$\mu_1 = (1/14)(f_5 + 2f_6 + f_7 + 2f_8 + f_9 + f_{10} + f_{11} + 2f_{12} + f_{13} + 2f_{14}) \quad (4)$$

$$\nu_1 = (1/6)(f_1 + 2f_2 + f_3 + 2f_4) \quad (5)$$

$$u = 2.993 + 2(W_2/W'_2) + 0.512(W_3/W'_3)/(0.512 + W_3/W'_3) \quad (6)$$

μ_1 and ν_1 are the mean partial correlation factors and are known functions of W_2/W'_2 and W_3/W'_3 . Their values as a function of W_2/W'_2 and W_3/W'_3 have been tabulated by Jones and Le Claire³. For weak perturbation approximation (WPA), all partial correlation factors are assumed to be equal to f_0 , hence $\mu_1 = \nu_1 = f_0$, the expression for b becomes

$$b = -6 + 6(W_2/W'_2) \quad (7)$$

Thus from the experimental value of b , W_2/W'_2 can be calculated, which in turn gives the value of u using equation (6). Now using the values of $D_1/D(o)$ and u , W_3/W'_3 and f_1 can be calculated from equations (2) and (3), respectively.

For calculations of W_2/W'_2 and W_3/W'_3 using without weak perturbation approximation (WWPA), method of iteration is employed in which assumed values of W_2/W'_2 and W_3/W'_3 are iterated using equations (1) and (2) and Tables of Jones and Le Claire³ (for reading values of μ_1 and ν_1 against the values of W_2/W'_2 and W_3/W'_3) till they are consistent with the experimental values of b and $D_1/D(o)$.

In model 2, values of b , $D_1/D(o)$ and f_1 can be written as functions of W_2/W'_2 and W_4/W_0 ,

$$b = -20 + 6(\mu_2/f_0) + 14(\nu_2/f_0)(W_4/W_0) \quad (8)$$

$$D_1/D(o) = (W_2/W'_2)(W_4/W_0)(v/f_0)/(v + 2W_2/W'_2) \quad (9)$$

$$\text{and } f_1 = v/(v + 2W_2/W'_2) \quad (10)$$

where,

$$v = 7 - (1 + 0.512 W_0/W_4)^{-1} - 2[1 + 3(0.512 W_0/W_4)^{-1} - [1 + 7(0.512 W_0/W_4)^{-1}]^{-1}] \quad (11)$$

$$\mu_2 = 1/6(f_{11} + 2f_{12} + f_{13} + 2f_{14}) \quad (12)$$

$$\nu_2 = 1/14(f_1 + 2f_2 + f_3 + 2f_4 + f_5 + 2f_6 + f_7 + 2f_8 + f_9 + f_{10}) \quad (13)$$

The mean partial correlation factors μ_2 and ν_2 as function of W_2/W'_2 and W_4/W_0 are given in a tabular form by Jones and Le Claire³. For weak perturbation approximation, all the partial correlation factors are equal, hence $\mu_2 = \nu_2 = f_0$ and equation (8) reduces to

$$b = -14 + 14 W_4/W_0 \quad (14)$$

Equation (14), thus gives the value of W_4/W_0 for WPA and hence v . The value of W_2/W'_2 and f_1

can be obtained after substituting the experimental values of $D_1/D(o)$ and W_4/W_0 , v and f_0 in equations (9) and (10), respectively. For without weak perturbation approximation, values of W_2/W'_2 and W_4/W_0 are calculated by the method of iteration⁴ as explained above.

The above expressions for b , $D_1/D(o)$ and f_1 have been formulated on the basis of vacancy mechanism. On the other hand, if this mechanism is not operative, the experimental value of b will be less than the minimum required to give a positive value of f_1 . The minimum value of b can be calculated in the following way. The expression for f_1 can also be written as

$$f_1 = 1 - 2(D_1/D(o)) \cdot (f_0/u) \quad (15)$$

$$f_1 = 1 - 2(D_1/D(o)) \cdot (f_0/v)(W_0/W_4) \quad (16)$$

for model 1 and 2, respectively. For f_1 to be positive, the above two equations give

$$u > 2f_0 \cdot D_1/D(o)$$

$$\text{and } v > 2f_0 \cdot D_1/D(o)(W_0/W_4)$$

The equality sign will give minimum value of u and v from which b can be calculated for models 1 and 2 using WPA and WWPA.

The values of certain jump frequency ratios W_2/W'_2 and W_4/W_0 for models 1 and 2, respectively, help to predict the solute-vacancy interaction if these ratios are less, equal or greater than 1 to explain repulsion, no interaction or attraction in the system. Expressions for calculating solute-vacancy binding energy $-\Delta g_r$ in terms of the enhancement factor b has been recently reported⁵ which are given below,

$$-\Delta g_r = RT \log \left(1 + \frac{b}{6}\right) \quad (17)$$

$$\text{and } \Delta g_r = 0.73 RT \log \left(1 + \frac{b}{6}\right) \quad (18)$$

Equation (17) is applicable when there is a solute-vacancy attraction while equation (18) for repulsion.

Discussion

On alloying, the diffusivity of the solvent will change and also, the variation of diffusivity with temperature will be different from the pure solvent. On alloying, Arrhenius equation, *i.e.* $D = D_0 \exp - Q/RT$, is generally found to be valid, however D_0 and Q will change. The increase of D_0 will increase the diffusivity and increase of Q will decrease diffusivity. Generally, it is found that on increasing the solute concentration both D_0 and Q either increase or decrease as could be seen from Table 1. It is further seen from Table 1 that this statement is valid not only for dilute alloys but for concentrated alloys⁶ also. The frequency factor D_0 is related to the entropy of formation and migration of vacancy; and activation energy to its enthalpy of formation and migration. It means

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF ZIRCONIUM SELF-DIFFUSION PARAMETERS IN DIFFERENT ALLOYS

Solute	Solute content* %	D ₀ (m ² /s ⁻¹)	Q (kJ/mole)	Temp. range K
V ^a	0.00	3.1 × 10 ⁻⁹	105.3	1 167-1 476
	0.50	4.5 × 10 ⁻⁹	109.0	1 167-1 476
	1.00	5.9 × 10 ⁻⁹	112.0	1 167-1 476
	1.50	9.3 × 10 ⁻⁹	116.8	1 167-1 476
	2.00	14.0 × 10 ⁻⁹	120.8	1 167-1 476
Cr ^b	0.00	6.8 × 10 ⁻⁹	145.0	1 218-1 518
	2.05	5.2 × 10 ⁻⁷	165.2	1 200-1 497
	3.49	2.1 × 10 ⁻⁶	169.0	1 196-1 518
	4.08	1.4 × 10 ⁻⁶	169.2	1 218-1 516
	7.86	1.6 × 10 ⁻⁶	173.4	1 227-1 516
Mn ^c	0.00	3.1 × 10 ⁻⁹	105.3	1 173-1 473
	0.50	7.1 × 10 ⁻⁹	112.3	1 173-1 473
	1.00	1.2 × 10 ⁻⁸	116.7	1 173-1 473
	1.50	2.2 × 10 ⁻⁸	121.8	1 173-1 473
	2.00	3.4 × 10 ⁻⁸	125.3	1 173-1 473
Fe ^b	0.00	6.8 × 10 ⁻⁹	145.0	1 218-1 518
	0.98	1.5 × 10 ⁻⁷	149.0	1 258-1 518
	1.35	2.1 × 10 ⁻⁷	150.9	1 218-1 515
	1.64	1.6 × 10 ⁻⁷	146.0	1 196-1 520
	3.54	2.9 × 10 ⁻⁷	140.8	1 188-1 470
Nb ^d	0.00	6.8 × 10 ⁻⁹	145.0	1 218-1 518
	1.05	3.8 × 10 ⁻⁹	110.5	1 173-1 473
	3.25	3.0 × 10 ⁻⁹	107.6	1 173-1 473
Sn ^e	0.00	2.4 × 10 ⁻⁷	159.0	1 173-1 473
	0.70	2.0 × 10 ⁻⁷	150.7	1 173-1 473
	3.30	3.0 × 10 ⁻⁷	163.2	1 173-1 473
	5.60	2.0 × 10 ⁻⁵	209.3	1 173-1 473

* Nb and Sn are by wt%. ^a Ref. 7. ^b Ref. 8. ^c Ref. 9. ^d Ref. 10. ^e Ref. 11.

that there is a tendency for the free energy of the system to remain constant.

At lower temperatures, the effect due to changes in Q will predominate while at higher temperature that due to the changes in D₀. Therefore, the Arrhenius plot of the alloy should intersect with that of the pure solvent at a temperature where the effect due to changes in D₀ annuls the effect due to changes in Q. However, it is generally not observed because the intersection temperature lies either

below or above the temperature under study as could be seen for Zr-Mn⁶ and V-Zr⁴ systems, respectively. The Arrhenius plots (Fig. 2) for the diffusion of Zr in Zr-(0-2 at % V) alloys⁷ intersect

Fig. 2. Temperature dependence of diffusion coefficient of ⁹⁰Zr in Zr-V alloys.

at ~1 223 K. Below the intersection temperature, the solvent diffusivity decreases with the solute concentration, and above it, it increases. This is the only system known which shows above behaviour.

From Tables 2 and 3, it is seen that there are two sets of dilute alloys. In the first one, b is less than and in the second one, b is more than the

TABLE 2—VALUES OF W₂/W'₂, W₃/W'₃ AND f₁ CALCULATED FOR MODEL 1 USING WEAK PERTURBATION APPROXIMATION (WPA) AND WITHOUT WEAK PERTURBATION APPROXIMATION (WWPA) FOR DILUTE ZIRCONIUM ALLOYS AT ONE TYPICAL TEMPERATURE

System	Temp. K	b	D ₁ /D(0)	WPA			WWPA		
				W ₂ /W' ₂	W ₃ /W' ₃	f ₁	W ₂ /W' ₂	W ₃ /W' ₃	f ₁
Zr-V ^a	1 167	-4.14	0.89	0.98	0.31	0.66	0.97	0.34	0.67
	1 223	0.00	0.94	0.92	1.00	0.74	0.93	1.00	0.74
	1 281	2.80	0.99	0.93	1.47	0.77	0.94	1.38	0.77
Zr-Cr ^b	1 273	5.95	13.10					(b min 32)	
Zr-Mn ^c	1 273	31.00	6.20	10.48	6.17	0.43	8.41	7.97	0.54
Zr-Fe ^d	1 273	98.6	91.90					(b min 270)	
Zr-Co ^e	1 203	94.30	384.00					(b min 1 095)	
Zr-Nb ^f	1 273	47.00	0.15	0.11	8.83	0.99	0.11	12.68	0.99
Zr-Sn ^g	1 273	83.80	1.40	1.09	14.97	0.94	1.06	23.07	0.96

*Calculations for these systems are approximate only because of non-availability of adequate data for low concentration (upto 2 at %)

^aRef. 7. ^bRef. 12. ^cRef. 9. ^dRef. 8. ^eRef. 13. ^fRef. 10. ^gRef. 11.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF W_s/W'_s , W_4/W_0 AND f_1 CALCULATED FOR MODEL 2 USING WEAK PERTURBATION APPROXIMATION (WPA) AND WITHOUT WEAK PERTURBATION APPROXIMATION (WWPA) FOR DILUTE ZIRCONIUM ALLOYS AT ONE TYPICAL TEMPERATURE

System ^a	Temp. K	b	$D_1/D(0)$	WPA			WWPA		
				W_s/W'_s	W_4/W_0	f_1	W_s/W'_s	W_4/W_0	f_1
Zr-V	1 167	-4.14	0.89	1.37	0.70	0.67	1.43	0.68	0.68
	1 223	0.00	0.94	0.92	1.00	0.74	0.92	1.00	0.74
	1 281	2.80	0.99	0.78	1.20	0.77	0.76	1.23	0.77
Zr-Cr	1 273	5.96	13.10	(b min 52)			(b min 42)		
Zr-Mn	1 273	31.00	6.20	4.03	3.21	0.35	3.03	3.60	0.41
Zr-Fe	1 273	98.60	91.90	(b min 578)			(b min 354)		
Zr-Co	1 206	94.30	384.00	(b min 2 555)			(b min 1 407)		
Zr-Nb*	1 273	47.00	0.15	0.03	4.36	0.99	0.02	5.51	0.99
Zr-Sn*	1 273	83.80	1.40	0.16	6.99	0.92	0.11	9.88	0.94

* Explanation as in Table 2. ^a References as in Table 2.

minimum required for the vacancy mechanism to be operative. For the first type of systems, calculations of jump frequency ratios and f_1 s are meaningless as negative values will emerge for W_s/W'_s , W_2/W'_2 and f_1 . This means that for this set, vacancy mechanism is not operative. It is further seen that f_1 s obtained by model 1 are higher or equal to those obtained by model 2 for positive b. This may be arising due to better approximation for model 1 (solute-vacancy interaction is considered upto second neighbours). It is also seen that f_1 s obtained by WPA are either equal or lower than WWPA. In WPA, the changes in the correlation factor for different types of jumps are neglected, however for WWPA, partial correlation factors are taken into account. The effect of this could be seen from Tables 2 and 3. When b is zero, all jump frequency ratios and f_1 s in both the models are same and the difference in the values of WPA and WWPA depends on the deviation of b from zero. Therefore, the solute-vacancy attraction or repulsion shown by W_s/W'_s or W_4/W_0 will remain unaltered in WPA and WWPA.

According to various investigators^{1,14-16}, the solute atom may be regarded as attractive (say) if a vacancy is more likely to jump from a given site, to sites nearer than farther off from the solute atom. On this basis, if both W_s/W'_s and W_4/W_0 are greater than 1, will show solute vacancy attraction, on the other hand, if they are less than 1, will show solute-vacancy repulsion. Because of attraction between solute and vacancy, vacancy is more likely to jump to second neighbour site where there is attraction than to third or fifth neighbour site where there is no interaction. Similarly for model 2, the vacancy is more likely to jump from second, (third or fifth) neighbour site to first neighbour site of the solute where there is attraction than to other sites where there is no interaction.

The jump frequency ratios W_s/W'_s and W_4/W_0 are linear functions of b (equations (7) and (14), respectively). Therefore, solute-vacancy interaction will be absent, attractive or repulsive based on the value of enhancement factor, b whether it is zero, positive or negative. From Tables 2 and 3 for Zr-V system, it is further seen that when b is negative,

zero or positive, the values of W_s/W'_s and W_4/W_0 are less than, equal to or greater than 1, respectively.

For WPA, solute-vacancy binding energy can be calculated from equations (17) and (18) using the values of b. It is seen from these equations, the value of b cannot be less than minus 6. The values of solute-vacancy binding energy for different solutes at one typical temperature of 1 273 K are given in Table 4. However, for Zr-V system, it is given at

TABLE 4—SOLUTE-VACANCY BINDING ENERGY IN ZIRCONIUM FOR DIFFERENT SOLUTES

System	Temp. K	b	$-\Delta G$ kcal mol ⁻¹	Type of interaction
Zr-V	1 167	-4.14	-1.98	Repulsion
	1 223	0	0	No effect
	1 273	2.51	0.88	Attraction
Zr-Mn	1 273	31.0	4.60	Attraction
Zr-Nb	1 273	47.00	5.51	Attraction
Zr-Sn	1 273	83.80	6.84	Attraction

three different temperatures as it changes sign from negative to positive at 1 223 K. This is the temperature at which all Arrhenius plots intersect as seen in Fig. 2.

Acknowledgement

Author acknowledges some of the calculations made by D. D. Pruthi.

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